

UAV communication aided by Intelligent Reflective Surfaces- A Performance Analysis in the context of Industry 4.0

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Abstract—Industry 4.0 enables the digital transformation of manufacturing and production industries through the integration of technologies, including cyber-physical systems, robotics, data analytics, and information and communication technologies. The provision of ultra-reliable low-latency wireless connectivity is vital for the uninterrupted operation of the underlying technologies and systems in smart factory settings. The harsh propagation environment within a smart factory due to a large number of scatters and obstacles represents significant challenges to reliable connectivity, high data rate, and low latency requirements. This paper presents a wireless communication solution enabled by unmanned aerial vehicles and intelligent reflecting surfaces for catering to the wireless communication needs of smart factories. The simulation results show the comparison of indoor and outdoor deployment of intelligent reflecting surfaces. Furthermore, a relation of cross-sectional area of reflecting surface to required bandwidth is shown graphically.

Index Terms—Reflective Intelligent Surface, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, industry 4.0, smart environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) opens the door for new technological trends and results in industrial transformation. Digitization is the key to adopting automation fuelled by big data and artificial intelligence. The key enabling technologies such as Industrial Internet-of-things (IIoT) [1], cyber-physical systems [2], augmented reality [3], big data [4], robotics [5], and UAVs [6] make this transition possible from conventional factories to smart factories. This endowment of digitization in I4.0 improves the overall industrial performance through intelligent actions driven by big data and ultimately stimulates scalability. Three main stages of transformation toward I4.0 are the digital connectivity of machinery and sensors, the development of smart product design and supply chains, and smart closed control loop digital operations [7].

The first stage of transformation toward I4.0 is the connectivity of machinery and data gathering from a large number of sensors. For massive connectivity, Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) is one of the solutions to accommodate the maximum number of users or sensors with

low-power and low-data rate requirements. The individual data rate requirements are low but cumulatively, the system data rate requirement becomes higher, resulting in a scarcity of bandwidth. Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency communication (URLLC) can provide uninterrupted connectivity by exploiting high-frequency bands in millimetre wave (mmWave) i.e., (IEEE 801.11ad and 802.11ay operate on 60GHz) [8]. The mmWave offers an abundant auxiliary spectrum in high-frequency bands (greater than 24GHz), addressing the spectrum's paucity, however, the highest attenuation due to oxygen absorption is a conceivable trade-off. A distributed antenna-massive Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (mMIMO) for indoor users in a smart factory is used to increase link reliability with reduce attenuation [9]. Nevertheless, system complexity and hardware impairments remain the impediments. Recently, a cost-effective solution called Intelligent Reflective Surfaces (IRS) in [10] has been proposed. IRS is also called Passive Holographic MIMO Surfaces (HMIMOS) [11]. IRS allows a smart ecosystem and provides connectivity with improved Quality-of-Service (QoS). With the help of the IRS, the uncontrollable dynamic feature is now considered a part of the network design paradigm.

In this article, we have considered UAV enabled communication network aided by passive IRS for indoor users. The signal performance is analysed at the User Terminal (UT) for indoor and outdoor IRS installation in the presence of indoor obstacles. In the existing literature, IRS is considered with Line of Sight (LOS) link with UT. However, we have acclimatised Non-LOS (NLOS) links in a more realistic scenario. Furthermore, relationship of cross-sectional area of reflecting signal with bandwidth is presented.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section II includes the working principle of IRS, section III includes a brief introduction to UAV enabled communication, section IV consist of used-cases of related works on IRS-aided UAV communication. Section V includes the proposed system model. Results are discussed in section VI. Finally, the article is concluded in section VII.

II. CONCEPT OF IRS

In principle, IRS is a software-controlled planer surface comprising many passive reflecting components. The reflecting elements with a smaller size than the wavelength of the incident signal can alter and modify the incident signal. The tuning of phase-shift and amplitude of the reflecting signal is controlled by a programmable smart controller such as a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), as interpreted in Fig. 1. As most of the reflecting surfaces are passive in nature, no power amplification, processing noise, and self-interference are considered [12]. However, recently active IRS is proposed to overcome the amplification issues [13], perceiving the Amplify and Forward (AF) phenomenon. Just like passive IRS, active IRS consist of a large number of small active reflecting surfaces, which are equipped with a negative impedance converter to amplify the power of the impinging signal [14]. Passive IRS can outperform the active IRS if installed at an optimal location. The passive IRS could be installed anywhere, however, it is recommended to install it near the receiver or transmitter to minimize path loss [12].

Fig. 1. IRS: Working principle

Inspired by the smart environment provided by the IRS, researchers considered it in integration with emerging wireless communication technologies such as Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) [15], Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transmit (SWIPT) [16], mmWave [8], Backscatter Communication (BackCom) [17], and UAVs. In this article, we have considered the UAV communication aided by IRS.

III. UAV COMMUNICATION

The essential applications of UAVs attracted researchers to use UAVs as part of communication networks. The main advantages of UAVs in wireless communication networks over terrestrial networks are mobility, high maneuverability, easy

deployment, and cost-effectiveness. In wireless communication networks, UAVs are considered Base stations (BS) and relays. The modeling of UAVs as BS in wireless networks is based on three-dimensional, unique scarce propagation and frequently changing deployments. In contrast to UAVs, terrestrial BS is considered a two-dimensional, well-established propagation, permanent and fixed deployment. Based on altitudes, the UAVs are classified into two, i.e., Low-Altitude Platform (LAP) and High-Altitude Platform (HAP). In most cases, LAPs are deployed as temporary BS in disastrous areas or bottleneck situations. Deployment of LAPs is easy, fast, and can be moved rapidly. However, HAPs can be deployed in remote areas where no terrestrial networks are working.

IRS importance surged recently in UAV-enabled wireless communication networks and researchers considering IRS and UAVs to create a virtual LOS between the transmitter and receiver. This will help us achieve greater throughput, low latency, and high connectivity with low-cost architecture.

IV. RELATED WORK

IRS can be used in the UAV communication network to enhance the QoS by improving the stochastic-based propagation environment. The important used cases in IRS-aided UAV communication are discussed in this section.

A. IRS mounted on UAV

IRS, in this case, is mounted on a movable UAV to create a virtual LOS link between transmitters and receivers, as shown in Fig. 2 (a). IRS-assisted UAV communication having NLOS link with terrestrial BS is considered for performance analysis [18]. The Numerical results are discussed regarding Symbol Error Rate (SER), Capacity, and path loss model for the case where IRS is mounted on a UAV. Similarly, performance graphs of outage probability, ergodic capacity, and energy are evaluated against the number of IRS elements mounted on UAV to provide virtual LOS in NLOS scenario [19].

B. Outdoor IRS in UAV-enabled communication

In this scenario, UAV is considered a BS and transmits the signal from air to the IRS, which is mounted on a building or anywhere outside the buildings, at a certain height as shown in Fig. 2 (b). A system model is considered in [20], which consists of multiple UAVs as BS, and IRS deployed on the ground at a certain height. They decompose the objective into three sub-problems, i.e., UAV placement and order designing for NOMA decoding, the composition of IRS matrix, and the optimization. The sum rate is maximized using Block Coordinate Descent (BCD)-based algorithm. The same system model is considered with Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) system mounted on UAV and energy consumption is optimized using KKT conditions [21].

C. Indoor IRS

IRS plays a vital role in smart indoor environments, specifically smart factories, where robots, manufacturing plants, and other machinery must communicate. Fig. 2 (c) shows the beam

Fig. 2. IRS and UAVs in different scenarios of wireless communication network

coming from the Access Point (AP) or BS and reflected by IRS towards the user equipment. The smart indoor environment was first introduced by L. Subrt and P. Pechac in 2012 [22]. They proposed an intelligent wall concept for indoor cognitive networks installed with active frequency selective surfaces. X. Tan et al., considered an indoor scenario where wall-mounted IRS is serving UTs having capability of selection of reflecting surfaces [23]. If the LOS link is broken due to an obstacle, the AP initiates the beam-search using the IEEE 802.11ad protocol, if not found, the IRS establishes a new communication link through the controlled reflective paths. In smart factories' indoor scenarios, robotic users communicate with each other and share the map plan for tracking purposes [20]. The mobile robot users do not necessarily lie in the LOS due to obstacles, so a passive IRS deployed on the wall is considered to provide virtual-LOS links to mobile robot users. Existing literature shows that the smart indoor scenario using IRS in UAV-enabled communication is not considered.

D. IRS and UAV assisted terrestrial network

Using UAVs and IRS in terrestrial networks, most of the system models are considered outdoors where UAVs functions as a movable relays for assisting terrestrial wireless communication networks. Ground BS is responsible for transmitting and receiving the information signal via UAV or IRS links. This scenario could be classified into two cases.

1) *BS-to-IRS-to-UAV-to-user link*: In this case, BS originates the information signal to the UAV and is interrupted by the large buildings. To ensure the LOS communication, IRS is installed on the large buildings, which reflect the impinging signal from the BS towards the UAV, then forward to the concerned user. In this scenario, the IRS is mainly considered close to the UAV.

2) *BS-to-UAV-to-IRS-to-user link*: The ground BS sends the information signal to the user through a UAV, which functions as a relay. It is considered that there is no LOS between the user and UAV due to trees or large buildings, so, IRS installed on buildings helps create a virtual LOS link between the user and UAV. This case can also be implementable to

provide reliable communication to indoor users. Both cases are portrayed in Fig. 2 (d).

From the existing literature, it is cleared that the indoor users with NLOS in UAV enabled communication is not considered. This article presents an IRS-aided UAV enabled communication for indoor users with an industry 4.0 perspective, and a performance analysis is carried out. Furthermore, IRS's indoor and outdoor deployment for indoor users is compared.

V. SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed system model consists of an indoor movable UTs, obstacles, IRS mounted on a wall, and UAV as Aerial BS (ABS). In this paper, we considered the UT with mobility up to $1\text{km}/\text{hour}$ and ABS is considered with the $3\text{km}/\text{hour}$ of mobility within a circular region, where the LOS link between IRS and ABS is not broken. IRS is mounted on the wall with an LOS between the ABS through a glass window and is considered to provide LOS to UTs, however, obstacles are also considered. Hence, there is a possibility that UTs has no LOS link with IRS and receive multiple copies reflected from scatters. Consider the passive IRS with N number of reflecting elements is mounted on height H , having LOS with ABS, and the coverage area is the indoor environment. The system model is given in Fig. 3. We assumed that the ABS and UTs are equipped with a single antenna.

Fig. 3. System Model of IRS aided UAV communication

We considered a rectangular IRS of size $L_x \times L_y$, mounted on a wall in a $x-y$ plane. Where L_x is considered three time of L_y and they are very large from λ i.e., $L_x > L_y \gg \lambda$, and λ is the wavelength of the impinging signal on IRS. The considered IRS has N small rectangular reflecting elements as shown in Fig. 4. A single element of size $l_x \times l_y$ is further composed of tiny units, i.e., $U_x U_y$, which are used for trading with the properties of the electromagnetic incident signal. These units are equipped with tuneable Radio Frequency (RF) switches or diodes and controlled by a controller, e.g., FPGA (for reference, Fig. 1). Total number of elements are $N = (L_x \times L_y) / (l_x \times l_y)$, and total number of units are $U = N \times U_x \times U_y$. The separation spaces U_s among tiny units are very small compared to the incident signal wavelength, i.e., $U_s \ll \lambda$, each element is considered continuous and can be illustrated as in Fig 5.

Fig. 4. Considered IRS structure

A downlink communication is considered for modeling and simulation and it is assumed that d_{ai} , d_{ir} , d_{is} , and d_{sr} as distances between the ABS and IRS, the IRS and UT, the IRS and scatter, and the scatter and UT, respectively. These distances are calculated using the Euclidean distance formula.

Fig. 5. An impinging signal on a metallic plate

According to our assumption, the ABS is in the far field, neglecting the curvature of the wavefront from ABS over the reflecting surface. This assumption make us able to approximate the impinging electromagnetic (EM) wave as a plane wave and is defined by the incident angle ψ_i ($\theta_i, \vartheta_i, \varphi_i$). The θ_i, ϑ_i , and φ_i are the representation of angle of elevation, azimuth, and polarization of the impinging EM wave, respectively, and $\theta_i \in [0, \pi]$. The IRS response function defines the received signal at UT, i.e., $h_r(\psi_i, \psi_r)$, where ψ_i is the incident angle of EM wave at IRS, and ψ_r is the Angle-of-Departure (AoD) at IRS. Here, ψ_r is defined as the function of the elevation angles and azimuth, represented as θ_r , and ϑ_r , respectively.

The free space path loss model is considered as a function of random channel gain that is defined by the IRS response

function, given in [24], i.e.,

$$PL_{IRS} = \frac{4\pi|h_r|^2}{\lambda^2} \times \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d_{ai}}\right)^2 \times \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d_{ir}}\right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $|h_r|^2$ is obtained from $h_r(\psi_i, \psi_r)$

$$h_r(\psi_i, \psi_r) = \sqrt{4\pi d_{ir}^2} \times \exp(jk d_{ir}) \times \frac{E_r(\psi_r)}{E_i(\psi_i)}, \quad (2)$$

where k is the wave number and can be written as $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$, $E_i(\psi_i)$, and $E_r(\psi_r)$ are the complex envelopes of electric fields of impinging EM wave and the reflected wave. In our system model, the term d_{ir} in eq. 1 is substituted by d_{tir} , which represents the total distance traveled by the signal from IRS to UT. This path could be the direct or indirect, i.e., IRS-to-scatters-to-UT.

To analyze the impact of IRS on the impinging signal under the assumption that is impinging EM wave is arbitrarily linearly polarized, the electric and magnetic fields are defined as [24]

$$\mathbf{E}_i(\psi_i) = E_i \times e^{(jk(\sin \theta_i \cos \vartheta_i)x + (\sin \theta_i \sin \vartheta_i)y + (\cos \theta_i)z)} e_x, \quad (3)$$

where, e_x is the unit vector in x -direction. The impinging wave is assumed to be in the y - z plane. Hence, the electric field direction is in the x direction.

$$\mathbf{H}_i(\psi_i) = \frac{E_i}{\eta} \times e^{(jk(\sin \theta_i \cos \vartheta_i)x + (\sin \theta_i \sin \vartheta_i)y + (\cos \theta_i)z)} \times \mathbf{d}_H, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{d}_H is the direction of the magnetic field, and η is the intrinsic impedance of the medium.

To find the \mathbf{d}_H , we need to find the polarization of the impinging EM wave. Suppose M_x and M_y are the x and y components of the magnetic field, polarization can be represented as $\varphi_i = \arctan \frac{M_y}{M_x}$. \mathbf{d}_H can be written as

$$\mathbf{d}_H = \text{sgn} \left(\frac{M_x \sqrt{\cos^2(\varphi_i - \vartheta_i) \sin^2 \theta_i + \cos^2 \theta_i}}{\cos \theta_i \cos \varphi_i} \right) \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i \cos \varphi_i}{\sqrt{\cos^2(\varphi_i - \vartheta_i) \sin^2 \theta_i + \cos^2 \theta_i}}, \frac{\cos \theta_i \sin \varphi_i}{\sqrt{\cos^2(\varphi_i - \vartheta_i) \sin^2 \theta_i + \cos^2 \theta_i}}, \frac{\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta_i \cos^2(\varphi_i - \vartheta_i) + \cos^2 \theta_i - \cos \theta_i}}{\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta_i \cos^2(\varphi_i - \vartheta_i) + \cos^2 \theta_i}} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$ is the Signum function and represents the magnetic field's direction.

Fig. 6. Squared magnitude of response function

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the considered system model, comparative performance analysis is carried out for indoor IRS deployment and outdoor IRS deployment to facilitate indoor users for industrial 4.0 applications. Fig. 7 shows the magnitude of the received signal for indoor and outdoor cases.

Fig. 7. Signal magnitude at receiver

The received signal at UT can be analyzed with the help of the Level-Crossing Rate (LCR). The LCRs of the received signal in both cases are given in Fig. 8 along with a comparison with the theoretical LCR. It is clear from Fig. 8 that IRS deployed indoors is better than the outdoor for indoor users, especially when there is a NLOS link between IRS and UT. Furthermore, the unwrapped phases of the received signals are given in Fig. 9.

After the comparative analysis, the squared value of magnitude at UT for specular θ_r is plotted in Fig. 6. We have considered $l_x = l_y$, and relation with λ is portrayed in Fig. 6. The peak in our case is at 58.287° ; however, theoretically, it should be at 60° . It is observed in the Fig. 6 that, when l_x and l_y increases, the response function shrinks.

Fig. 8. Level-Crossing Rate in indoor IRS and Outdoor IRS

According to the antenna theory, i.e., bandwidth and antenna aperture are inversely proportional. Hence, increasing the size of the reflecting surfaces affects the bandwidth indirectly, and significant interference can be observed. From Fig. 6, it is analyzed that when the cross-sectional area of the reflecting sheet approaches λ , the bandwidth becomes sufficiently large, resulting in perfect estimation.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have analyzed the IRS performance for the indoor user for industrial 4.0 applications in UAV-enabled wireless communication networks. N number of passive reflecting surfaces, each with a size much lesser than λ with specular reflection, are considered. The spacing between these minor units is considered sufficiently small such that the reflecting surface acts as a continuous surface. In terms of signal strength and Level-Crossing Rate (LCR), IRS performance on UT is compared. Furthermore, the relation of the reflecting surfaces to λ , i.e., the wavelength of the impinging signal, is drawn. The two main observations in our work are, proved that indoor

Fig. 9. Unwrapped Phases at receiver

installation of IRS gives better results than outdoor installation and the effect of the cross-sectional area of the reflecting surfaces. This work can be extended to find the optimal position for IRS installation for specular and anomalous reflections.

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